

Innovative Technological Pedagogies Towards Transformative Learning Post Covid-19: A Case Study

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Abstract

To reimagine the new pedagogical approaches and possibilities and to make them fit in the frame of the contemporary educational scenario, the adaptation to the innovative strategies through all-encompassing teaching methodology was the need of the hour. Robust instructional method is a course plan procedure that helps in making our classes, tasks, and evaluations as impermeable to interruption as it could be expected. If we want to frame and inculcate this kind of pedagogy in our schools, the best way is to consider paying a little heed to which methodology is being used while teaching on web (Internet), face to face, or hybrid way? In numerous specific situations, innovation can give learning progression, even when the understudies cannot actually be present in the boundaries of their classroom or if it is a experiential and project-based learning. Also, there are numerous hindrances to fruitful online learning driven by innovation, including educator readiness, admittance to online assets and gadgets, and students' practice in the home. In this paper, a case study of an educational institution in Uttar Pradesh has been analyzed where the situation and circumstances have been examined with reference to the teaching-learning practices and methodologies used before, during and after the COVID scenario.

Keywords: Pedagogies, Innovations, Accessibility, Transformative learning, Adaptability, Experiential learning, ubiquities learning.

Introduction:

Innovations in teaching-learning have always been the prime focus of any educational institute. Especially during the pandemic, when teachers and students, all over the globe were exposed to the new and possibly lasting changes instead of the conventional methods of instructing and learning. Hence came into existence, the need to limit instructive interruption by moving on to technology-based instructional practices and figuring out how to guarantee manageable, high-caliber and adaptable educating and learning which would have been a distant dream without utilization of innovation.

Earlier, teachers had to exert themselves by spending hours in writing lesson plans and then executing it by repeating the content delivery in classrooms. The pedagogy used was completely teacher-driven having least impact on the students' minds. But, with the change in dimensions of methodology, the tables have turned. In the era of online learning, teachers, with the help of technology are capable of bringing tremendous positive changes in the students' outcome.

The 21st century skills that this paradigm shift facilitates helps learners to be determined and fearless as they move ahead in life. It endeavors a pedagogy that promotes out of box thinking and encourages the young learners to emerge as individuals with discerning minds.

Learning is not only about e-learning but focus is on ubiquities learning *i.e.*, "everywhere learning"-fulfilling the requirements of E-learning's motto of 'anytime, anywhere and any context' along with 'virtual learning', 'blended or hybrid learning', 'collaborative and constructive learning', 'M-learning' *i.e.*, mobile learning which is "learning across multiple contexts, through social and content interactions, using personal electronic devices etc. by means of self-paced learning. These new tools and strategies

are to be implemented over the 'sit and get' approach of learning, to actively engage the accustomed global learners of the 21st century. All these flexible and innovative strategies, help in improving the teaching-learning process by active involvement of every child resulting in the holistic development of the child. The main idea of the saying is that technology should be used in a way that helps students learn about machines without being machines *i.e.*, becoming too much reliant on them.

Faces of Transformational Pedagogies:

From traditional classroom teaching to online teaching, from blackboards to interactive whiteboards and from textbooks to iPads, information technology in education has transformed the educational system by providing it a global platform. Technology has made our learning world smaller and accessible. With emerging technologies in education, and change in perception of learning schools have also integrated technology in the classroom to enhance better learning and teaching, leading to technology changing education.

Transformation into the information technology has changed the educational system in a big way by making it more accessible globally and by transforming the way content is delivered - from traditional classroom teaching to online teaching, from blackboards to interactive whiteboards, and from textbooks to iPads. With technology, our learning world has become smaller so that anyone can have access to education from a global perspective. It has rapidly changed the landscape of education, with new technologies emerging every day that have the potential to revolutionize the way we learn and teach. Schools have been quick to integrate these technologies into the classroom in order to improve learning outcomes and keep up with the demand of 21st century learners. With technology, a 10-year-old child could easily have access to information about rocket science and other complex topics - there's no limit to what they can learn today!

Curriculum, is no longer just a document. It is an effective way to explore and discover new knowledge. It is a question to be answered, an answer to be modified, a change to be adopted and a challenge to be handled wisely. Learning gaps can be addressed in a better way by using differentiation tactics or strategies. Tutors, TV programs and books have been replaced by Google, YouTube and Blogs.

It shows that change is something that happens constantly and it can be difficult to keep up with. It's volatile, frequent, rapid, unseen, and unexpected but it's also inevitable. The way we think about things, the way we learn, and the way we parent have all changed. It's no longer a one-way conversation but a multi-way conversation.

The Digital India campaign is helping to digitally empower the entire nation, as mentioned in Chapter 23 of NEP 2020, 'Technology Use and Integration in NEP 2020'. Technology will play a key role in improving educational processes and outcomes, and education will be critical in transforming the nation into a knowledge economy. The relationship between technology and education is bidirectional, with each impacting the other.

The goal of technology in education is to improve teaching, learning and evaluation processes, as well as to support teacher development and enhance educational access. Technology can also streamline educational planning, management and administration - for example by simplifying processes related to admissions, attendance and assessment. (Retrieved from <https://shikshan.org/nep-2020/technology-integration/>)

Technology in education is gaining of knowledge as well as wisdom to handle multiple tasks, so here, addition along with the deletion of the thought process continues as and when the shift is required. A multitasking techno-savvy educator of 21st century must be able to create computational thinking among the students by using blended and scaffolding mode of teaching learning by transferring the academic ownership to the learners by using experiential learning, art integrated learning, embodied learning, learning by gamification etc.

Development of Metacognitive skills:

Since innovation plays a crucial role in creating a sustainable future, innovation in education is of particular importance. Innovation in the classroom is a vehicle for progress which is enhanced by implementing a PBL (Problem based learning) because it inculcates transferrable skills e.g., self-

management, IT skills, critical thinking, communicating, collaborating, teamworking, numeracy etc. by finding and using purposeful and appropriate learning resources. By using the design-thinking approach, and the problem-solving method of invention - students become more innovative by experiencing inspiration, clarification, evaluation, distillation, incubation and perspiration.

It helps in pedagogy by developing the cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains.

Cognitive domains: It facilitates learning, helps in analyzing, cooperates learning by new ideas.

Affective domains: It develops interest in learning and helps learning by new ideas.

Psychomotor domains: It provides real-life environment by using multimedia and reduces physical effects.

Comparative Case-Study of Paradigm Shift before and after Pandemic:

Keeping in view the impact of ICT based technology on education system; a case study was conducted. The purpose of the study was to find out the effectiveness of the online resources for teaching learning process, to invent the strategies to attain the goal of digital literacy in an integrated way and the necessity to identify the skills helping in the digital age which consists of reading and writing along with online communication. With the intention of solving the purpose efficiently, the methods and pedagogies used in an educational institution with respect to the Pre and Post COVID applications were focused.

Teachers who are using ICT and are multi facilitators, being well aware of its efficient implications, help in promoting the interdisciplinary result-oriented approach by guiding the needs of the students and exploring new possibilities in the teaching-learning process.

Before the pandemic, mode of teaching-learning used by the teachers during the offline classes was altogether different from that of the online classes which was forced to be implemented with the sudden closure of everything including the schools due to COVID-19. Teachers were under great pressure and apprehension of losing their dominance over the classroom procedures and teaching learning activities which was making this transition even more difficult. Hence, the strategy was planned out in such a way so as to make the teaching-learning process easier and simpler by starting with a blended mode of teaching-learning practices using the advanced e-learning techniques. The age-driven cognitive, social, psychological and emotional needs of the students were taken into consideration, while making the tentative changes in the curriculum according to their needs and the existing circumstances.

The challenges faced before starting this study with the technological advancements in the institution were studied and analyzed; and the proposed remedial actions suggested are mentioned below:

1. Challenges for students' fraternity:

- a. **Adaptability:** The transition from traditional classroom to online platform was quite difficult for them to adapt.

Remedial Action: By using multimedia tools, adaptive learning was used by adjusting the syllabus and curriculum according to the individual needs. For this purpose, personalize attention was provided by teachers to them. It was after identifying their weaknesses and strengths.

- b. **Computer knowledge:** Technological advancements in the form of online classes, were a totally new and different concept for them. In the beginning, many of them were not very much techno-savvy to handle even the simple computer related operations required for teaching learning e.g., MS Word, PowerPoint etc.

Remedial Action: In such cases, students were provided the support and guidance by the teachers to access those devices by contacting them through call, email or live chat.

- c. **Availability of resources:** The main constraint in the learning process was the unavailability of the minimum required resources to the students needed for attending the online classes.

Remedial Action: In such cases, teachers provided the notes and other useful learning materials to the students at their homes with the help of their parents and relatives.

- d. **Time management:** It requires intensive hard work for the students to get acquainted with the online learning for better learning outcomes.

Remedial Action: Teachers assisted such students by contacting them individually and provided the possible technical support- related to software and the academic tools for making the learning effective.

- e. **Health Issues:** As reported by most of the parents, students were facing health issues after following the new mode of attending the school i.e., by means of using the online classes.

Remedial Action Parents were suggested to fix the screen timings of the students. School time table was made in such a way so that students were getting 10 minutes break after every period and overall online class timing should not exceed 2 to 3 hours duration depending on the class.

- f. **Self-motivation & confidence:** Since they were used to of face-to-face communication with their teachers in the classrooms, they were facing difficulty in understanding the classroom activity and explanations by the teachers and adapting the new learning styles. Due to lack of confidence and concentration, they were unable to understand the live classes hence found it difficult to make assignments and project works using ICT.

Remedial Action: Teachers were also trained to understand the specific learning styles of such students i.e., by interaction or communication, audio and visual presentations and provided them individual assistance.

2. Challenges faced by the teachers:

- a. **Engaging students:** Using a new learning platform which was equally challenging for teacher too.

Remedial Action: Giving personalized attention by means of using various techniques e.g., gamification, giving them enquiry-based assignments and projects e.g., preparing blogs and posts etc., using quizzes and podcasts to stimulate students' interest. Teachers provided personalized feedback to the students to identify their weakness.

- b. **Computer knowledge & Technical issues:** It was a biggest challenge for the teachers as during the offline teaching, they were not using the technological devices and were not very much user friendly with those tools and techniques.

Remedial Action: The teachers who were not having an expertise in handling computers were able to perform all the tasks efficiently within no time after attending the FDP and workshops organized by the institution.

In view of all these circumstances, the school managing committee took certain measures to bring the desirable changes for a better outcome from all its stake holders for transition, transmission, transportations and revolution in the existing educational scenario. A support system was developed by involving the students, their parents, teachers and the other community members. The parents who were cooperating with the school in counseling, assisting and motivating their children for adapting the new technology-based education in an effective way were encouraged and felicitated with special rewards and certificates. Also, the students who had shown tremendous improvement were given the certificates of achievement.

Figure 1: Impact of Innovative Pedagogies on Teachers' Performance

Teachers were encouraged by awarding them for their excellent work.

In this way, the school management adopted the design thinking strategy by identifying hurdles in the way of ICT based advanced methods of teaching-learning by empathizing, defining (the problem), ideating, prototype, and testing as mentioned in figure 1.

Hence, the school started providing live tutorial meetings and sessions, live streaming of seminars and class-lectures, pre-recorded audio and video files of lectures, virtual one-to-one student-teacher-parent meetings, and prompt feedback exercise.

Teachers were giving online sessions by using advanced technologies like Zoom, Google Classrooms, WhatsApp, Skype and Virtual Labs etc. along with using audio-visual such as creating videos using documents, excel sheets PDFs, PowerPoint slides, quiz, discussion forums for students, jam boards, whiteboard features, gaming features etc. to make teaching and learning more interactive, with instant analysis and feedback, grading of assignments, exams, etc. which were equally enjoyed by the students by learning from hands-on experiences. It enhanced the competencies like *willingness to run risks, decision-making in critical situations, critical thinking, perseverance, and built-up entrepreneurial attitude* in students. Decision of framing and implementing the innovative strategies was made in context with the competency expectations, reinforcing best practices in the area of study, best practices in professional ethics and conduct, laying the base for the next level of learning experience and providing a basis for lifelong development of such skills after graduation for the students in order to not only succeed but excel.

Methodology:

The methodology used in this case study was qualitative in nature. The study was supported by a purposive sample consisting of 16 teachers and 181 students from all classes of elementary and secondary school and the data collected was tabulated, analyzed and interpreted as mentioned below:

Table 01: Professional Qualifications of Teachers

	Primary School	Upper Primary School	Secondary School	Percentage
Total number of teachers	7	5	4	100
No. of Graduate Teachers	5	2	0	43.75
No. of Post graduate teachers	2	3	4	56.25
No. of Computer Savvy Teachers (Before Pandemic)	1	2	2	31.25
No. of Computer Savvy Teachers After Pandemic)	7	5	4	100

From the table 01, it can be concluded that the percentage of computer savvy teachers was raised from 31.25 % to 100% after the pandemic which indicated towards a successful transformation of teaching fraternity towards advancement in technological skills as per the need of the hour.

Table 02: Teaching practices and activities conducted in Pre-COVID and Post-COVID time (in 2020-21) in Percentage (%)

Sl.	Teacher's Activity	Teaching practices and activities conducted in pre-COVID time (in 2019-20) in %			Teaching practices and activities conducted in post-COVID time (in 2019-20) in %		
		Quite often	Sometimes	Rarely /Never	Quite often	Sometimes	Rarely /Never
1	Made a daily/weekly lesson plan in details?	65	30	5	70	30	0

2	Prepared any customized audio/video file for teaching?	0	5	95	95	5	0
3	Used any TLM other than the textbook during a class?	20	30	50	80	20	0
4	Talked to a parent about the child's learning on daily basis?	10	70	20	90	10	0
5	Used the smart board on regular basis during a class?	30	40	30	100	0	0
6	Made children work in small groups during a class?	25	20	55	65	25	10
7	Played game/sports with students?	60	20	20	75	20	5
8	Did a class activity, not mentioned in the textbook?	5	15	80	80	15	5

The comparative data mentioned in the table 02 infers that a good number of teachers became more aware and advanced in understanding the need and implementation of the teaching practices and activities in the class on regular basis in the new normal.

Table 03: Students performance before pandemic during the offline class (Teacher driven class)

Class	No. of Stu.	Academic Outcomes						Behavioral Outcomes			
		No. of students Scoring 40-60%	%	No. of students Scoring 61-80%	%	No. of students Scoring 81-100%	%	No. of students showing disciplined behavior	%	No. of students showing undisciplined behavior	%
I	21	4	19	10	47.6	7	33.3	14	66.7	7	33.3
II	32	6	18.8	18	56.3	8	25	20	6.25	12	37.5
III	24	5	20.8	13	54.2	6	25	19	79.2	5	20.8
IV	16	4	25	8	50	4	25	12	75	4	25
V	26	5	19.2	13	50	8	30.8	21	80.8	5	19.2
VI	15	2	13.3	10	6.67	3	20	12	80	3	20
VII	10	1	10	7	70	2	20	7	70	3	30
VIII	15	2	13.3	11	73.3	2	13.3	12	80	3	20
IX	22	4	18.2	15	68.2	3	13.6	16	72.7	6	27.3

Table 04: Students performance after pandemic during the online class (Student driven class)

Class	No. of Stu.	Academic Outcomes						Behavioral Outcomes			
		No. of students Scoring 40-60%	%	No. of students Scoring 61-80%	%	No. of students Scoring 81-100%	%	No. of Disciplined Students	%	No. of Undisciplined Students	%
I	21	0	0	12	57.1	9	42.9	21	100.0	0	0.0
II	32	0	0	20	62.5	12	37.5	31	96.9	1	3.1
III	24	2	8.3	15	62.5	7	29.2	22	91.7	2	8.3
IV	16	0	0	10	62.5	6	37.5	15	93.8	1	6.3
V	26	1	3.9	15	57.7	10	38.5	24	92.3	2	7.7
VI	15	1	6.7	11	73.3	3	20	15	100.0	0	0.0
VII	10	0	0	8	80	2	20	9	90.0	1	10.0
VIII	15	2	13.3	11	73.3	2	13.3	14	93.3	1	6.7
IX	22	2	9.09	16	72.7	4	18.2	20	90.9	2	9.1

After analyzing the above-mentioned tables 03 and 04, it can be concluded that ICT has created a great impact on the teaching learning environment in the current scenario in terms of students' academic and behavioral aspects.

Table 05: Comparative analysis of teaching learning Environment

	Pre-COVID	During COVID	Post-covid
Focus on	teachers	Learners	Group
Role of learner	Passive	Active	Adaptive
Technology	Chalk and talk	Personal Comp.	PC + Network

The table 05 shows how the teaching-learning environment is changing by shifting the focus from teacher-centric to collaborative learning. How the role of learner is changing from a passive learner to an adaptive learner along with the pedagogy of technology-based teaching consistently shifting from pre-covid time to post-covid time.

The ICT based innovative pedagogies adopted by students, teachers, parents and the school management were proved beneficial after following the remedial measures keeping in view the roles and responsibilities of teachers', students'; and the change in the pattern of syllabi and curriculum delivery as mentioned below:

Table: 06- Change in Teachers' responsibility

Pre-COVID Time	Post- COVID Time
Knowledge transmission	Guidance & facilitation of knowledge
Controlling classroom environment	Creating classroom environment
An expert all the time	Co-learner with the skill of collaboration
Learning the use of ICT	Using ICT for improved learning
Didactic & expository approach	Interactive, experiential & exploratory approach

Table: 07- Change in Students' Responsibility

Pre-COVID Time	Post- COVID Time
Passive i.e., inactive learner	Active learner
Reproducing knowledge	Producing new knowledge
Teacher-dependent learner	Self-dependent autonomous learner
Solitary & introvert learner	mutual learner
Only learning	Learning to learn, think, design, create & communicate

Table: 08- Changes in the pattern of Curriculum

Pre-COVID Time	Post- COVID Time
Rote learning	Inquiry-based learning
Rigid (Fixed time & space)	Flexible (anytime and anyplace)
Single direction progression	Progression in multiple paths
Monologue mode of communication	Dialogue and collaborative mode of communication
Resources of analogue type	Resources of digital type

Thus, it is summarized that the key process to learning for a student is not only to gain an access to the knowledge and the resources but to share and extend the acquired knowledge by becoming an autonomous learner, in order to attain the objective of transformative learning.

Conclusion:

We've made a lot of progress in the shift from focusing on learning styles to personalized learning. But it is important to know where the student is currently at in their learning progression? What do they need to know in order to further their development? And, how can they monitor their own learning progress for self-efficacy? It is also important for the learners (students) to be aware of the reasons why and how they are going to learn, this will allow them to take ownership of their own education.

To imply the effective teaching and learning strategies- games, audio-visual materials, real world learning, brainstorming creative and innovative ideas, team challenges, choice of activity, taking the lesson out of the classroom, and simulations are important aspects. For this, the first step is to map out a scope and sequence of socio-emotional learning skills that students need to progress. This will in turn increase their emotional intelligence, leading to improved academic and social performance, as well as decreased emotional distress. When necessary, it should be paired with specific intervention strategies as mentioned below:

1. Issuing an invitation to inquiry in order to help increase students' interest.
2. Building background knowledge to satisfy students' curiosity.
3. Exploring ideas that interest the students to help them manage any uncertainty they might feel.
4. Helping them identify an inquiry question and deciding on a direction for the inquiry to encourage optimism in them.
5. Finding information from a broad range of sources and thinking about it broadly and deeply to create confusion or frustration, but it's important to push through these doubts.
6. Reflecting on, making meaning, and creating communications from the information leading to clarity, a sense of direction, and confidence.
7. Sharing our learning with others and learn from their feedback, whether it's positive or negative.
8. Evaluating what we've learned and whether we've achieved our goals, then reflecting on the content and process.

It's important that pedagogies and methodologies include real-world changes and be solution-oriented which will help learners embrace mistakes and failures, and accelerate their learning so that they are more prepared for life.

Rightly said by DengeCours, technology will never be able to replace great teachers but for sure, those teachers who are not techno-savvy and are still lagging behind in the race of multitasking, are definitely going to be replaced by the techno-expert multitasking teachers. The data mentioned in the study indicates about the importance of creative and innovative IT-based-technologies by comparing the pre and post COVID time duration and revealed that even the pandemic situation will get over, the blended mode of teaching and learning will be replacing the traditional approach.

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